

Regulating Data Sharing across MQTT-based Internet of Things Ecosystems

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Abstract

Nowadays, numerous Internet of Things (IoT) applications handle personal data, often relying on smart objects which can be even worn by the users. Some IoT apps start to exploit data resulting from the interaction of devices that operate in different ecosystems. Although favoring the definition of advanced services, these forms of data sharing raise serious security risks, such as the uncontrolled disclosure of confidential data across multiple ecosystems. So far this issue has only been partially addressed, as most of the research efforts on access control for IoT have been focused on single IoT ecosystems. Therefore, in this work we do a step to fill this void, by proposing an ABAC framework to control data sharing across MQTT-based bridged ecosystems. The proposed enforcement mechanism regulates data exchange among IoT devices of pairs of bridged ecosystems on the basis of access control policies and user preferences. Experimental analyses show the efficiency of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Access control; Internet of Things; MQTT; ABAC; Bridged Ecosystems.

1. Introduction

Internet of Things (IoT) applications are starting to be massively integrated into our lives [1], providing advanced analysis services leveraging on data generated by different IoT devices. A variety of IoT application domains exist. For instance, the analysis of data generated by wearable sensors allows highly customized forms of training in the domain of Internet of Sports applications (e.g., see the RAIS project¹), or it allows real time monitoring of patients health conditions in the healthcare domain [2]. Even though the benefits of these services are manifold, a trade-off between service utility and user privacy need to be taken into consideration [3], as these applications represent a potential threat to user privacy [1].

In the last years, research has coped with this issue by proposing several data protection solutions for IoT. In particular, for what access control is concerned, different approaches have been designed (see Section 8 for a compendium). For instance, many access control solutions have been proposed for cloud-enabled IoT applications, which leverage on a centralized infrastructure that controls the communication and the activities of any node of an ecosystem (e.g., [4, 5, 6, 7]). Other access control frameworks target IoT applications designed to control device behavior at the edge of the system [9]. However, the majority of these approaches aims at regulating the access to

data generated and exchanged within a single ecosystem (e.g., [10, 11]).

In contrast, an increasing number of IoT applications rely on IoT devices distributed across multiple ecosystems. For instance, Wang et al. [12] propose a collaborative edge computing framework for vehicular networks, which, by means of inter-ecosystem and intra-ecosystem collaborations, allows data sharing among network edges. Similarly, Zhang et al. [13] propose an edge computing framework, which, by means of virtual views of the data built by data owners for specific end-users, allows users of different ecosystems to share data.

Distributed architectures have the advantage of enabling parallel forms of data processing, as well as extending the scope of the sensed data to multiple ecosystems [14]. In addition, the independence from a centralized cloud-based infrastructure favors better performance. However, along with these potential benefits, distributed approaches bring serious security/privacy threats, such as the possible disclosure of reserved data to unauthorized devices of other ecosystems.

In this paper, we do a first step to address this issue, by proposing an ABAC framework to regulate data sharing among interconnected MQTT-based IoT ecosystems.² Due to the pervasivity of many IoT scenarios, the proposed approach provides support for fine grained, context based access control policies. For instance, let us consider the case of MyPersonalTrainer, an Internet of Sport (IoS) application developed for MyGymBrand, a brand of affil-

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¹RAIS (Real Time Analytics for Internet of Sports), EU H2020 Marie Curie ITN project, <https://rais-itn.eu/>

²The choice of MQTT (<http://docs.oasis-open.org/mqtt/>) is due to its wide diffusion.

iated sport halls, which allows gym frequenters to share data about training sessions of different sport disciplines. In particular, when deployed on exercise bikes, the app allows them to participate to cycling races, sharing data, such as the current speed, and the covered distance. An access control policy that regulates data sharing across gyms may limit the exchange of rider performances to the race duration, granting the access only to the set of users registered for the race.

In addition, to enhance user control on the data generated by the administered devices, our framework allows users to specify their own preferences, which might restrict the privileges granted by access control policies. For instance, rider Mary wishing to enforce a stricter privacy protection, may specify a user preference that, during a competition, filters out the identifiable data from the data shared with the riders of other gyms.

The framework proposed in this paper extends the one proposed by us in [11], where we design an Attribute-based access control (ABAC) model to control the communication of IoT devices operating in a single MQTT-based ecosystem. In contrast, the enhanced framework proposed in this paper allows regulating data sharing across multiple ecosystems on the basis of access control policies and user preferences. This requires a substantial extension of the original framework, by introducing a decentralized approach to the enforcement of access control policies which regulate message exchange among bridged ecosystems, and which can be specified in each side of bridged ecosystem pairs. In addition, to empower users with a better control of the access to data forwarded to external ecosystems, the proposed framework also allows the enforcement of user preferences within ecosystems different from the ones where the same preferences have been originally specified. This is an important requirement when data originated from IoT devices span the boundaries of the organization where they have been originally collected. For instance, Bob, who is a rider of the MyGym sport hall, may specify a user preference that allows gym coaches of any associated sport hall to only access his/her performance data. Our framework integrates an enforcement monitor, which regulates data sharing, operating as an MQTT broker proxy that alters the communication flow between interconnected ecosystems. The monitor can be easily integrated into existing MQTT deployments, with basic configuration activities. The efficiency of the monitor prototype has been experimentally assessed, showing a reasonably low enforcement overhead in different testing scenarios.

To the best of our knowledge, the framework proposed in this paper is among the earliest edge-based access control approaches that allow regulating data sharing across interconnected IoT ecosystems. We are only aware of another pioneering work by Carranza and Fong [15], which proposes an approach to regulate the interaction of message brokers of different ecosystems. However, [15] does not support context based policies, operates at coarse grained

level, and does not allow users to customize data sharing on the basis of their preferences.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 shortly presents background information related to MQTT, whereas Section 3 presents the adopted access control model. Section 4 provides an overview of the proposed solution. Section 5 introduces the enforcement mechanism. In Section 6 we discuss relevant implementation details, whereas in Section 7 we present the experimental evaluation. Section 8 surveys related work. Finally, Section 9 concludes the paper.

2. Background

This section describes basic concepts related to MQTT, and core aspects of the access control framework proposed in [11], which allows regulating clients communication within a single MQTT ecosystem.

2.1. MQTT

MQTT enables peers communication by means of the publish/subscribe architecture. MQTT *clients* communicate with other clients through a *message broker*. A client can either request the broker to publish a message on a *topic*, or to subscribe the receiving of messages on topics matching a *topic filter* expression. Brokers forward messages by means of topic based routing criteria. On receipt of a publishing request on a topic t , the broker analyzes the topic filters of the active subscriptions, and forwards the message to any client who has subscribed a topic filter expression that matches t .

Example 1 Let us consider again the IoS app MyPersonalTrainer introduced in Section 1. Let us suppose that MyPersonalTrainer allows gym frequenters who are enrolled in a training session ts to share their running performance. In particular, suppose that the smart treadmills of the sport halls MyGym and RemoteGym, which integrate multiple sensors and a tablet, also host an instance of MyPersonalTrainer which has been configured to publish messages specifying runner performances on the topics: $tr/performance/ts/speed$, $tr/performance/ts/avgspeed$, $tr/performance/ts/length$, $tr/performance/ts/duration$, $tr/performance/ts/heartbeats$, where tr and ts are placeholders for a treadmill and a training session identifier. The same devices have also been configured to subscribe the receiving of performance data of all users attending ts , specifying $+/performance/ts/+$ as topic filter. In addition, the app deployed on gym coaches' tablets allows them to monitor performance data of gym frequenters. The app has been configured to subscribe the topic filter $+/performance/#$, so that coaches can receive performance data published by any treadmill within any training session.

Clients interact with the broker exchanging control packets. The list of packets supported by MQTT is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: MQTT control packets

<i>Control Packet</i>	<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>CONNECT</i>	cp_{CN}	Client requests a connection to a Server
<i>CONNACK</i>	cp_{CA}	Acknowledge connection request
<i>PUBLISH</i>	cp_{PB}	message
<i>PUBACK</i>	cp_{PA}	Publish acknowledgement
<i>PUBREC</i>	cp_{PRC}	Publish received
<i>PUBREL</i>	cp_{PRL}	Publish release
<i>PUBCOMP</i>	cp_{PC}	Publish complete
<i>SUBSCRIBE</i>	cp_{SB}	Subscribe to topics
<i>SUBACK</i>	cp_{SA}	Subscribe acknowledgement
<i>UNSUBSCRIBE</i>	cp_{US}	Unsubscribe from topics
<i>UNSUBACK</i>	cp_{UA}	Unsubscribe acknowledgement
<i>PINGREQ</i>	cp_{PRQ}	PING request
<i>PINGRESP</i>	cp_{PRS}	PING response
<i>DISCONNECT</i>	cp_{DS}	Disconnect notification

On receipt of a connection request cp_{CN} from a client c , a broker opens the connection and acknowledges c of the established connection issuing a cp_{CA} packet. On receipt of cp_{CA} , c may request: i) to *publish* a message, issuing a packet cp_{PB} , ii) to *subscribe* the receiving of messages on topics that match a *topic filter*, issuing a packet cp_{SB} , iii) to *unsubscribe* a previously subscribed topic, sending a packet cp_{US} , or iv) to *disconnect* from the broker issuing a packet cp_{DS} .

An MQTT broker can be configured to connect to remote brokers, enabling the communication of clients belonging to different ecosystems. Brokers supporting these communication forms are hereafter referred to as *bridging brokers*. A bridging broker is therefore a broker configured to connect to a target remote broker with which it shares messages published by clients of the respective ecosystems. The interaction is regulated by means of *bridging rules*. A bridging rule br specified for a bridging broker bb is a tuple $\langle rb, tp, dr, qos, lp, rp \rangle$, where rb denotes the remote broker representing the target of bb , tp is a topic filter expression specifying the topics of the messages to be shared by bb ; dr specifies the sharing direction (*in*, *out*), which can be *in*, if br allows bb to receive messages from rb , or *out*, if br allows bb to send messages to rb ; qos specifies the QoS level to be used for the message exchange; finally, lp and rp are local and remote prefixes, which are used by bb to remap the topic of outgoing and incoming messages, respectively. If br specifies *in* as sharing direction, bb prepends tp with rp and subscribes to the resulting topic on rb . On receipt of a message m from rb whose topic matches the subscribed topic, bb substitutes the remote prefix rp prepending the topic of m with lp , and forwards m to the local clients who subscribed to a matching pattern. In contrast, if br specifies an output sharing, bb prepends tp with lp and subscribes the resulting topic on the local broker. On receipt of a message m published by a local client, whose topic matches the subscribed topic, bb substitutes the local prefix with rp , and forwards m to rb .

Example 2 Let us consider again the scenario pre-

sented in Example 1, and suppose that MyPersonalTrainer also enables users to share performance data with a remote analysis server that allows comparing them with previously tracked data of the same user, of users attending the same course, of frequenters of the same gym, or runners attending any sport hall of MyGymBrand. Suppose that MyGym hosts a broker, which handles the communication among its gym apparatus, as well as with brokers of the associated gym RemoteGym, and of the data analyzer ecosystem, which hosts the remote analysis server.

Examples of bridging rules are the following:

$br_1 = \langle Analyzer, +/performance+/speed, out, 0, "", MyGym \rangle$, $br_2 = \langle RemoteGym, +/performance+/speed, in, 0, "", "" \rangle$.

br_1 enables the forwarding to the analyzer ecosystem of messages specifying the current speed of a runner that attends a training session. The remote prefix *MyGym* denotes the provenance of the message. The remote analysis server is a client of the analyzer ecosystem which subscribes the receiving of messages on topics that match the filter $+/+/performance/\#$, which allows the server to access performance data of the frequenters of any gym. In contrast, on the basis of br_2 , MyGym broker subscribes the receiving of messages from RemoteGym that refer the speed of a runner attending any training session of the associated sport hall.

2.2. Access Control Enforcement within a single MQTT-based IoT ecosystem

We now summarize the approach we proposed in [11], to regulate MQTT clients communication in a single ecosystem. The solution relies on an ABAC model for MQTT ecosystems, and consists of an enforcement mechanism designed for the model, and implemented by an enforcement monitor, which can be easily integrated into MQTT-based ecosystems.

2.2.1. The ABAC model

The choice of ABAC [16] has been mainly based on its diffusion, and well founded flexibility (e.g., see [17]). ABAC is based on the concepts of subject, object, and environment, which respectively model: i) a subject who sends access requests, ii) a protected resource, and iii) the context within which an access request has been issued.

In our context, ABAC is used to regulate the reception and the publishing of messages, on the basis of access control policies and user preferences.

MQTT clients, possibly on behalf of a user, connect to a broker with the aim to exchange messages with other clients. Once connected, a client can request to publish a message on a topic, or to subscribe the receiving of messages on topics that match a topic filter (see Section 2). Clients are therefore *subjects* requiring to access messages (i.e., to publish or receive), which represent protection *objects*, within an *environment*, namely a model of the execution context from which the access request has been issued.

A subject s is characterized by attributes that specify properties related to the client, and possibly the user on behalf of whom the client sends access requests. Since MQTT clients requiring to connect to a broker need to specify a client identifier, s includes an attribute cid specifying the client identifier. Additional attributes can then be introduced, such as the attributes uid and rid that model the identifier and role of the user on behalf of whom the client sends publishing or subscription requests. Attributes can also refer client properties. For instance, an attribute dev may be used to characterize the device that hosts a client.

Application messages represent protection *objects*. Since MQTT brokers route messages on the basis of the message topics, an object o , modeling a message m , includes an attribute tp , that specifies the topic of m . However, other attributes can be introduced as well to specify additional properties of the message, such as, for instance, the category of data in the payload (e.g., sensitive, personal or generic, cfr. [18]).

Depending on the considered application scenario, a message delivering context can be modeled with different sets of attributes, which may represent, for instance, time, location and purposes. For the sake of simplicity, in this paper, we consider an environment e characterized by a single attribute t that models the message delivery instant.

The model proposed in [11] supports *access control policies*, specified by security administrators, as well as user defined policies, denoted as *user preferences*, which restrict the privileges granted by access control policies. Access control policies grant subjects the read or write access to messages on given topics. Read privilege represents the subject right to receive messages on a subscribed topic, whereas the write privilege allows a subject to publish a new message. User preferences enable highly customized forms of data protection, serving single user needs. In-

deed, multiple users may publish data on the same topic, but each user can have a different perception of the sensitivity of the published data, and may desire to protect the access to his/her data accordingly.

Example 3 Let us consider our running example. Access control policies are used to constrain the type of data which can be published and received on behalf of MyGym frequenters, independently from a specific running session. For instance, an access control policy may authorize MyGym coaches to access, through their app, any information that is published by frequenters of the gym, and frequenters to only see the average speed, running length, and duration of other runners registered for the same gym course. However, users may wish to restrict the privileges granted by access control policies, constraining, through user preferences, the set of data which can be shared during a running session (e.g., the current and average speed), as well as the receivers of these shared data. For instance, a user preference specified by Bob, a frequenter of MyGym, may forbid John, a coach of MyGym, to access the tracked data.

Access control policies and user preferences are specified with predicates defined over subject, object and environment attributes, which constrain the contexts within which the privileges specified by access control policies and user preferences can actually be exercised.

Definition 1 (Parametric predicate). *A parametric predicate is a boolean expression built by composition of subject, object and environment attributes, mathematical operators ($>$, $<$, $=$, $+$, $-$, $*$, $/$, $\%$), logical operators (\wedge , \vee , \neg), set operators (\in , \subset , \subseteq , \cap , \cup , \setminus), logical quantifiers (\forall , \exists), and predefined functions allowing the processing of attributes values.*

Definition 2 (Access control policy). *An access control policy p is a tuple $\langle s, tf, exp, pr \rangle$, where s refers the subjects constrained by p ,³ tf specifies a topic filter expression, exp is a parametric predicate,⁴ whereas pr specifies the read /write privileges granted to s if exp is satisfied.*

Example 4 Let us consider a policy p_1 which grants frequenters enrolled to a gym course the privilege to publish performance data and read performance data of other trainees, and a policy p_2 , which allows gym coaches to access performance data of gym frequenters during their working hours. p_1 can be specified as: $\langle frequenter, +/performance/ts/+, isEnrolled(s.sid), rw \rangle$, where $isEnrolled(s.sid)$ is a function that checks whether the subject $s.sid$ is enrolled to a gym course, whereas p_2 is modeled as $\langle gymcoach,$

³For the sake of simplicity, in this work s can refer to a client, user or role identifier. However, the approach can be extended providing support to intensional binding expressions defined by composition of subject attributes.

⁴If no restriction is required, the predicate should specify a tautology.

$+/performance/+$, $isWorkingTime(t,s.sid)$, r), where $isWorkingTime(t,s.sid)$ is a function that checks whether the time referred to by t matches the work shift of the subject.

User preferences constrain the access to messages published by a user, on the basis of parametric predicates.

Definition 3 (User preference). A user preference up is a tuple $\langle uid, tf, sub_exp \rangle$, where uid specifies the identifier of a user who wishes to protect the access to messages published by any of the clients it handles, whereas tf specifies a topic filter expression which denotes the messages, among those that have been published on behalf of uid , to which the preference applies, whereas sub_exp is a parametric predicate specifying a precondition to the receiving of a protected message to be satisfied by the subscribed clients.

Example 5 The user preference $up_1 = \langle Mary, +/performance/ts/+, s.sid = \text{“coach”} \wedge s.uid = \text{“Alice”} \rangle$ specified by Mary, a frequenter of MyGym limits to Alice, a coach of MyGymBrand, the privilege to access Mary’s performance data related to the training session ts .

User preferences restrict the read access privileges which are granted by access control policies. Therefore, a subscriber subject s can read, at time t , a message m published by a user u on a topic tp iff: i) there exists an access control policy p that grants s read access to tp at time t , and ii) there exists at least one user preference up among those specified by u with a topic filter expression that is matched by tp , which grants s read access to tp .

2.2.2. Access control enforcement

Policies and preferences are enforced through a monitor that operates as a proxy between an MQTT message broker and multiple clients, and a key-value datastore, which manages access control policies and user preferences to be enforced by the monitor. An high level view of the system architecture is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: An high level view of the system architecture in [11]

A key advantage of the proposed enforcement approach is that it does not rely on ad-hoc defined clients or brokers, as it supports any client and broker complying with the MQTT specification. The enforcement monitor is the only component which can connect to the server, on behalf of the client. The approach can be used in heterogeneous

environments composed of different versions of clients and brokers.

The monitor intercepts any control packet issued by the clients and the broker, and forwards them to the respective receivers, except for packets representing connection and publishing requests, for which additional activities are executed. Connection requests trigger subject profiling activities, and the opening of communication channels with the requesting client and the broker, which are controlled by the monitor. Message publishing requests issued by clients via monitoring channels are handled by initially deriving the policies that regulate the publishing of messages by the requesting subject. If no policy is satisfied the request is blocked. In contrast, if the publishing operation complies with at least one policy, the monitor derives the preferences specified by the user on behalf of whom the publishing has been requested. The monitor then embeds the derived preferences into the payload of the publishing request, and forwards the packet to the local broker.

Publishing requests issued by the broker are handled in a similar way. Any broker request is received through a previously opened communication channel connecting the broker to a subscriber. The monitor extracts attributes and user preferences from the packet’s payload, derives the subject, object and environment attributes modeling the context within which the message should be received by the subscriber, and evaluates the preferences wrt the derived attributes. If no preference is satisfied, the request is blocked, whereas if at least one preference is satisfied the monitor derives the applicable access control policies. In case the read access complies at least with one of the policies, the monitor removes from the payload all previously embedded metadata and forwards the packet to the subscriber, otherwise it blocks the request. More details can be found in [11].

3. Access control across different MQTT-based IoT ecosystems

To manage data sharing across different IoT ecosystems, we enhance the model in [11], with the ability to regulate message exchange among MQTT publishers and subscribers possibly belonging to different ecosystems.

In what follows, we refer to a scenario where two MQTT-based ecosystems, respectively referred to as *local* and *remote*, communicate to each other by means of *interconnected brokers*. We denote two brokers as interconnected when one of them has been configured as bridging broker and specifies the other one as connection target.

The main differences with previous model version are related to subject, access control policies and user preferences.

A subject s can denote : i) a client of the local ecosystem who connects to the local broker with the aim to publish or receive messages, possibly on behalf of a user,⁵ ii)

⁵MQTT allows specifying a user name within CONNECT con-

it can be a local broker of one ecosystem which aims at exchanging application messages with a remote ecosystem, or iii) a bridging connection through which a bridging broker communicate with a remote broker. A local broker may forward messages published by its local clients to a remote broker, as well as receive messages published in a remote ecosystem which then will be forwarded to the rightful subscribers of its ecosystem.

As in [11], access control policies are specified to grant subjects the read or write access to messages referring to a set of topics. Like in [11], if the subject is a client, the read privilege represents the right to receive messages on a subscribed topic, whereas the write authorization specifies the right to publish a new message. In contrast, if the subject is a broker or a bridging connection, a read authorization represents the right to receive messages that have been published in a remote ecosystem, whereas a write authorization specifies the right to forward messages to a remote ecosystem. Policies granting read/write privileges to a broker are specified by the security administrators of the ecosystem that hosts the broker. Although access control policies that regulate broker activities show some similarities with bridging rules, they differ from the latter in that bridging rules: i) can only grant authorizations to bridging brokers, whereas access control policies can also target standard (non bridging) brokers, ii) route messages only on the basis of their topics, whereas access control policies enable a context aware ABAC based forwarding regulation, and iii) are used to configure topics remapping abilities of bridging brokers.

Def. 1 and 2, are still applicable to formalize the concepts of parametric predicate and access control policy. The only difference is that component s of p in Def. 2 can also refer to a broker, or to a specific connection of a bridging broker. If s refers to a broker, the read/write privilege granted by p models the broker privilege to receive/forward messages. If s refers to a bridging connection, the granted privilege applies to the bridging broker that handles the connection specifying the broker communication ability for this connection.

Example 6 Let us now focus on policies regulating brokers interaction specified for our running case. A policy $p_3 = \langle \text{MyGym}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \text{isOpeningHour}(t), \text{rw} \rangle$ authorizes MyGym’s broker to forward and receive messages encoding performance data of runners attending a training session ts during MyGym’s opening hours. The privilege applies to any bridging connection, as no bridging connection is explicitly referred to within p_3 .⁶ A similar policy, p_4 , can be specified for the RemoteGym’s broker

control packets (see Table 1), with the aim to support authentication mechanisms. However, user names are not mandatorily specified.

⁶Alternatively, the pair of policies $p_{3a} = \langle \text{MyGym.RemoteGym}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \text{isOpeningHour}(t), \text{rw} \rangle$, and $p_{3b} = \langle \text{MyGym.Analyzer}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \text{isOpeningHour}(t), \text{w} \rangle$ might have been used to constrain MyGym’s broker ability to communicate through its bridging connections.

as $\langle \text{RemoteGym}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \text{isOpeningHour}(t), \text{rw} \rangle$. In contrast, a less restricting policy can be specified for the Analyzer’s broker as $p_5 = \langle \text{Analyzer}, +/\text{performance}/\#, \text{true}, \text{r} \rangle$. This policy authorizes the Analyzer’s broker to receive, from any MyGymBrand’s gym, messages on topics referring performance data of any training session.

Users can further constrain the access to messages published on their behalf, through user preferences. In the extended model, user preferences can either restrict the read access to published data by clients, or brokers forwarding privileges.

For instance, users may specify user preferences requiring that their running data are only shared within the sport hall where data have been sensed, without being tracked, analyzed, or forwarded to frequenters of other gyms.

In order to allow users to restrict brokers forwarding privileges, the user preference definition (see Def. 3) has been enhanced with an additional component, denoted bp , which allows specifying the forwarding preference. bp may refer to: i) the name of a target ecosystem te , if up constrains the forwarding to te only, ii) $*$, if up constrains the forwarding to any remote ecosystem, or iii) \perp , if up applies to the read access to the referred messages by subscriber clients. On the basis of bp , the parametric predicate exp specifies a precondition: i) to the forwarding of a protected message to a remote ecosystem, or ii) to the receiving of the message by rightful subscribers.

Example 7 The user preference up_1 introduced in Example 5 can be redefined as: $up_1 = \langle \text{Mary}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \perp, \text{s.rid} = \text{“coach”} \wedge \text{s.uid} = \text{“Alice”} \rangle$. It is worth noting that during Mary’s training session, depending on the work shift, Alice may be working within MyGym or RemoteGym, however, the effect of up_1 is independent from the gym where Alice works when Mary is training. In addition, Mary, who does not agree to be tracked by the analysis server, specifies the preference $up_2 = \langle \text{Mary}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \text{Analyzer}, \text{false} \rangle$, which prohibits the sharing of her training session data with that server. Let us also consider the user preference $up_3 = \langle \text{Bob}, +/\text{performance}/\text{ts}/+, \text{RemoteGym}, \text{false} \rangle$, specified by Bob, a frequenter of MyGym. up_3 prohibits the forwarding of Bob’s performances during the training session ts to RemoteGym.

User preferences restrict the privileges which are granted by access control policies, constraining the reading privileges of subscribed clients, and the broker ability to forward messages to a broker of a different ecosystem. More precisely, a subscriber subject s of a given ecosystem re can read a message m published on a topic tp by a publisher subject ps operating within re on behalf of a user u iff within re : i) there exists an access control policy p that grants s read access to tp and ii) either a) there exists at least one user preference up , among those specified by u with a topic filter expression that is matched by tp , which

grants s read access to tp , or b) no user preference up specified by u refers to a topic filter expression that is matched by tp . In case s and ps belong to different ecosystems, additional checks are required to allow the forwarding of m from the ecosystem of ps to the one of s . Let us denote with se and pe the ecosystems of s and ps , respectively, whereas b_{pe} and b_{se} denote the brokers of these ecosystems. b_{pe} can forward to b_{se} a message m published on a topic tp by a subject ps of pe on behalf of a user u iff within pe : i) there exists an access control policy p_w that grants b_{pe} the write access to tp , and ii) either a) there exists at least one user preference up among those specified by u with a topic filter expression that is matched by tp , which grants b_{pe} write access to tp , or b) no user preference up specified by u has a topic filter expression that is matched by tp and grants b_{pe} write access to tp . A message m forwarded by b_{pe} can be received by b_{se} iff within se there exists at least one access control policy p_r that grants b_{se} read access to tp .

Example 8 Let us suppose that Mary and Bob are registered to a course of MyGym, and that they are attending the training session ts , which, within RemoteGym, is coached by Alice. Let us assume that Bob and Mary are running on the treadmills tr_1 and tr_2 , which have been configured to share performance data of all runners attending the training session (see Example 1). The publishing and receiving of data is regulated by policy p_1 (cfr. Example 4), which grants any frequenter that is enrolled to a gym course and is attending a training session ts , the privilege to publish messages specifying his/her performances, and to receive messages over topics specifying performance data of other runners attending ts . The publishing by tr_1 and tr_2 of messages referring Mary and Bob performances during ts , complies with p_1 , therefore, both tr_1 and tr_2 are authorized to publish. However, the user preference up_1 specified by Mary, constrains the receiving of messages published by tr_1 (see Example 7), as no frequenter or coach, but Alice, can access Mary's data. Therefore, on the basis of the applicable policies and preferences, during ts , Mary can see Bob's performance, whereas Bob cannot see Mary's data. According to policy p_3 (see Example 6) performance data published by tr_1 and tr_2 can be forwarded by MyGym broker to any remote ecosystem. However, the forwarding of Mary's and Bob's data is constrained by the user preferences up_2 and up_3 (see Example 7). More precisely, due to up_2 , Mary's data cannot be sent to the Analyzer's broker, however, no preference prohibits the forwarding to RemoteGym. In contrast, on the basis of up_3 , Bob's data cannot be forwarded to RemoteGym, but no restriction has been specified for Analyzer. The receiving of Mary's forwarded messages by the RemoteGym's broker is regulated by policy p_4 (see Example 6), which authorizes, during the opening hours of RemoteGym, the receipt of messages over performance related topics referring to the training session ts , which have been forwarded by MyGym's broker. Similarly, according to p_5 , Analyzer

can receive messages over performance related topics of any training session which have been forwarded by MyGym's broker, thus it can also receive Bob's data.

Once the forwarded message m is received by b_{se} , m can be dispatched to the rightful subscribers of se . More precisely, m can be accessed by a subscriber subject s of se iff: 1) within se there exists at least one access control policy p_r which grants s the read privilege to messages on topics that match a topic filter expression that is also matched by tp , and 2) the access complies with at least one of the user preferences specified by the original publisher of m within pe .

Example 9 Let us now focus on the routing, within the RemoteGym ecosystem, of messages on performance related topics, which have been originally published by treadmill tr_1 on behalf of Mary, and then forwarded to the RemoteGym ecosystem by MyGym's broker (see Example 8). Alice's app, has been configured to subscribe the receiving of performance data published by any device (see Example 1). However, the receipt is regulated by the applicable access control policies and user preferences. More precisely, the receiving requires the joint satisfaction of the policy p_2 (see Example 6), which grants Alice the privilege to receive messages on performance related topics during her working shift, and the user preference up_2 (see Example 7), specified by Mary, which grants the access to Alice only. Due to up_1 , no client within MyGym and RemoteGym is authorized to access Mary's data, but those requesting the access on behalf of Alice.

4. Overview

As explained before, we target an application scenario where two MQTT-based ecosystems, each composed of multiple MQTT clients and a local broker through which these clients communicate, need to share data. Inter-ecosystem communication is achieved by configuring the local broker of one of the two ecosystems as a bridging broker specifying the other broker as connection target.

The proposed framework enhances the approach introduced in [11], which targeted the regulation of message flow within a single ecosystem, with the ability to regulate the communication of MQTT clients of different IoT ecosystems. More precisely, the enforcement monitor proposed in [11], denoted in what follows as *local* monitor, has been enhanced to enforce user preferences possibly specified within a different ecosystem. Additionally, a new enforcement monitor, denoted as *bridging monitor*, has been designed, which, on the basis of access control policies and user preferences, regulates message passing between interconnected brokers.

The proposed approach requires to interpose the local monitor between the local clients and the respective brokers, and the bridging monitor in between the brokers of the interconnected ecosystems. More precisely, 1) the clients of each ecosystem are configured to connect to the

Figure 2: An high level view of the system architecture

respective monitors rather than directly to their brokers, 2) the local monitors are connected to the respective local brokers, 3) the local broker, which has been configured as a bridge, specifies the bridging monitor as connection target, and 4) the bridging monitor specifies the local broker of the other ecosystem as connection target. As such, the local monitors of the connected ecosystems behave as proxies of the respective brokers, and are the only components that can communicate with the brokers on behalf of their clients. In contrast, the bridging monitor behaves like a proxy of the broker referred to as connection target of the local bridging broker, and is the only component enabling the communication between different ecosystems. Figure 2 presents an high level view of the system architecture. The designed approach does not require ad-hoc implementations of clients and brokers, and it is independent from specific client and broker versions. The local and bridging monitors can also operate within heterogeneous environments, where different versions of clients and brokers cooperate.

According to the system architecture shown in Figure 2: 1) local MQTT brokers are deployed in different trusted LANs, whereas 2) MQTT clients in untrusted external networks, 3) whereas the local monitors and the bridging monitor are hosted by DMZ proxies at the LAN interfaces. Firewalls placed at the interfaces of these three DMZ proxies are configured to prohibit unmediated connections with the local brokers.

The activities of the local and bridging monitors are subject to access control policies and user preferences (cfr. Section 3) regulating the communication within each ecosystem, and between interconnected ecosystems. Access control policies and user preferences are handled by key-value datastores, deployed in the interconnected ecosystems. The policy set handled by each datastore allows regulating the internal communication in the respective ecosystem, as well as the messages exchanged with the other ecosystem. The bridging monitor accesses the policy sets of both datastores, whereas the local monitors only the set in the datastore of the respective ecosystem.

5. Enforcement

In order to ensure that the internal message flows, as well as those across different ecosystems comply with the specified access control policies and user preferences, the local monitors analyze and possibly alter the flow of MQTT control packets exchanged by their clients, whereas the bridging monitor performs similar operations on the flow of packets exchanged by the brokers of the two ecosystems. In the remainder of this section, we first present the rationale of the enforcement mechanism, and then we focus on its specification details.

5.1. Enforcement rationale

The message passing within a target ecosystem is regulated by instances of the enforcement monitor proposed in [11] and summarized in Section 2.2.2, which have been enhanced to enforce user preferences possibly specified within a different ecosystem. The enhanced version of the monitor differs from the original one for the management of security metadata, instrumental to access control. Indeed, different from [11], during the analysis of client publishing requests, along with the user preferences, the monitor embeds into the analyzed packet's payload the subject, object, and environment attributes that model the context within which the publishing request has been issued. These embedded attributes are necessary as user preferences could refer to the context within which a message has been originally published, along with the context within which the message is accessed. For instance, in our running case a user preference specified by a gym frequenter could introduce a time to live constraint that authorizes the read access to performance data within 2 seconds from the publishing, thus requiring to keep track of the publishing time. Similarly, a user preference could also refer to the attributes related to the specifying subject. For instance, a preference specified by gym frequenter could restrict the access to his/her performance data to frequenters of the same gym or of other gyms who are using the same type of exercise machine (e.g., a treadmill or a rowing machine). The evaluation of this preference requires the access to a subject attribute which denotes the exercise machine employed by the user who has specified the preference. Finally, a user preference could also refer to object attributes, such as the topic of a message which in turn denotes the type of data sensed by an exercise machine (e.g., step rate). Since a bridging broker could remap message topics when forwarding a message to a bridged ecosystem (e.g., it could prepend the identifier of the ecosystem where the message has been originally published, see Section 2), object attributes that keep track of the original message topic are required to evaluate the preference within the ecosystem that has received the forwarded message.

During the analysis of publishing requests the monitor extracts all these attributes along with user preferences from the packet's payload, deriving the context in which: i) the message has been originally published, and ii) should

be received by the subscriber. The monitor evaluates the embedded preferences wrt all derived attributes. Finally, before issuing a message to a rightful and authorized subscriber, the monitor removes from the packet’s payload all previously embedded metadata.

Let us now focus on the communication between ecosystems, which is regulated by the bridging monitor. By assumption, the local broker of one of the two ecosystems has been configured as a bridging broker specifying the bridging monitor as connection target.

Message sharing between the two ecosystems is subject to the bridging rules that configure the communication abilities of the local brokers (cfr. Section 2). Hereafter, we refer to bridging rules whose component dr has been set to *out* as *output bridging rules*, and to *in* as *input bridging rules*. Output bridging rules specify the topics of the messages published within the local ecosystem that can be forwarded to the broker of the other ecosystem, and the remapping criteria with which the topic of a message is modified before the message is actually forwarded, whereas input bridging rules specify the topics of the messages published within the connected ecosystem which the local broker subscribes to receive, and the criteria with which the topic of the received messages is remapped before they are forwarded to a rightful local subscriber. As a first step, the local broker of the ecosystem where the bridging monitor is hosted sends a connection request to the bridging monitor, which in turn forwards the request to the local broker of the other ecosystem, as it was the original sender of the request. If the request is accepted, a communication channel connecting the two local brokers is open, which is controlled by the bridging monitor. In what follows, we denote as *connecting broker* the local broker that sends the connection request, whereas the other is denoted as *target broker*. Through the established channel, the connecting broker sends a subscription request for any input bridging rule,⁷ and then waits for control packets issued by local clients and by the bridging monitor.

The bridging monitor has been designed to forward any control packet received by the local brokers to the respective receiver, except packets encoding publishing requests which require additional operations.

Let us first consider publishing requests originating from the ecosystem managed by the connecting broker. For any received publishing request issued by a local client that matches an output bridging rule, the connecting broker remaps the topics of the packet (see Section 2) and forwards the request to the bridging monitor. On the packet reception, the bridging monitor extracts from the payload: 1) the user preferences specified by the subject who has originally requested the publishing, and 2) the attributes that model the publishing request context.⁸ Then,

⁷Each subscription request specifies as topic filter the concatenation of the remote prefix (see Section 2.1) and the topic filter of the considered input bridging rule.

⁸Such data have been added to the payload by the local monitor.

the bridging monitor selects from the extracted preferences those constraining message forwarding to the other ecosystem, and evaluates them wrt the derived attributes. If no preference is satisfied, the message is blocked. Otherwise, if at least one preference is satisfied, the bridging monitor enforces the applicable access control policies. More precisely, it selects from the policy set of the ecosystem managed by the connecting broker those policies regulating the forwarding of messages to external ecosystems, and from the policy set of the ecosystem managed by the target broker those policies regulating the receiving of messages from external ecosystems. If the forwarding complies with at least one policy of both sets, the message is sent to the target broker, otherwise the forwarding is forbidden. In contrast, the target broker, upon receiving a publishing request from the bridging monitor, forwards, on the basis of the message topic, a copy of the received packet to communication channels that connect the broker to the rightful subscribers of the other ecosystem, each controlled by the local monitor. For any message receiver candidate, the monitor checks whether the considered subscriber, on the basis of the preferences in the message payload and the applicable access control policies, is authorized to receive the message, and, in this case, it removes all metadata from the payload and forwards the packet.

Similarly, the target broker forwards to the bridging monitor any publishing request received from a local publisher that matches a previously subscribed topic filter.⁹ The bridging monitor handles the publishing request with an approach symmetric to the one just described for the opposite message flow. The only difference is related to the local broker management of publishing requests from the bridging broker. Indeed, due to the remapping criteria specified by the input bridging rules, the topic of the message is remapped before the message is forwarded to the channels, controlled by the local monitor, which connect the broker with rightful local subscribers.

5.2. The enforcement mechanism in details

We start to consider configuration aspects enabling broker to broker communication within the system architecture introduced in Section 4, which are instrumental to the proposed enforcement mechanism.

Let us hereafter refer to the bridging monitor as bm , and let us denote as lb the local broker that has been configured to operate as bridging broker specifying the bridging monitor bm as connection target, whereas we denote with rb the broker of the other ecosystem.

On behalf of local clients, and on the basis of the configured bridging rules (cfr. Section 2), lb can publish messages to rb , and can subscribe the receiving of messages published within rb ’s ecosystem.

The interaction of lb and rb starts with a connection request cp_{CN} , sent by lb . Upon receipt of cp_{CN} , the bridging

⁹We remind that any subscription is achieved on behalf of the local broker on the basis of an input bridging rule.

monitor bm extracts the credentials of lb from the *CONNECT* control packet, and forwards the packet to rb . rb authenticates the subject and replies with a *CONNACK* control packet cp_{CA} , which is received by bm and then forwarded without any modification to lb . cp_{CA} specifies whether the connection request has been accepted or refused by rb , and, in the latter case, the cause. If cp_{CA} encodes the acceptance of the connection request, lb can start communicating with rb .

Once the connection has been established, for any input bridging rule ibr that has been specified for lb , lb sends a *SUBSCRIBE* control packet cp_{SB} to rb , specifying as topic filter the expression resulting from the concatenation of the components rp and tp of ibr . bm receives cp_{SB} and forwards it to rb , which keeps track of the topic filter $rp+tf$, and sends back a *SUBACK* packet notifying the receiving of the request. Once received by bm , the acknowledgement is forwarded to lb , which, on the basis of the specified bridging rules, is now ready to forward messages published by its local clients to rb , as well as to receive messages published in the rb 's ecosystem.

We now focus in more details on the enforcement mechanism implemented by the bridging monitor, whose joint work with the local monitors allows regulating the communication of clients belonging to different ecosystems.

Let us start to consider the forwarding of messages published within lb 's ecosystem. The payload of any publishing request cp_{PB} received by lb includes: 1) the user preferences, if any, specified by the user, on behalf of whom the message has been published, and 2) the subject, object, and environment attributes which model the context within which the publishing request has been issued. If the topic tp referred to by cp_{PB} is matched by an output bridging rule obr of lb , lb remaps the topic, prepending to tp the remote prefix rp of obr . The resulting control packet, referred to as $cp_{PB'}$, is then forwarded to bm , which, by assumption, has been specified as connection target of lb . Upon the receipt of $cp_{PB'}$, bm extracts from the packet's payload the user preferences and the subject, object, and environment attributes. For any included user preference up , bm checks whether up constrains the forwarding of $cp_{PB'}$ to the ecosystem managed by rb , and, in such a case evaluates the parametric predicate exp of component bp of up (see Section 3) with respect to the extracted subject, object, and environment attributes. If the predicate of at least one of the user preferences that constrain the forwarding is satisfied, bm checks whether there exists at least one access control policy among those specified in the ecosystem of lb that authorizes the forwarding, and at least one in the policy set of the ecosystem of rb that authorizes the import, otherwise the forwarding is blocked. The selection of the applicable policies in both ecosystems is achieved by matching the topic filter of any policy p specified for bm , with the topic of $cp_{PB'}$. Policies are evaluated with respect to the attributes extracted from the payload. If the parametric predicate of at least one policy is satisfied, bm forwards $cp_{PB'}$ to rb , which in turn sends

cp_{PB} , to its local monitor. The local monitor then handles the publishing request as described in Section 2.2.2. The approach used by the bridging monitor to regulate the forwarding of messages published within the ecosystem managed by rb is similar to the previously explained one. The only difference is related to the topic remapping task operated by lb . Indeed, on receipt of a publishing request cp_{PB} from the bridging monitor bm , lb , on the basis of the specified input bridging rules, first redefines the topic of cp_{PB} removing the remote prefix, and then forwards the packet to the local monitor which will handle the request (see Section 2.2.2).

6. Implementation

We now shortly discuss implementation aspects of the bridging monitor.¹⁰ An high level view of the bridging monitor architecture and of the related control flow is shown in Figure 3. The bridging monitor bm has been designed to listen for connection requests from lb .¹¹ Upcoming connections requests are handled by a connection handler, which, on receipt of a new request from lb , opens a communication channel cc_{lb} with the local broker, and one channel cc_{rb} with rb , the local broker of the other ecosystem. The handler also instantiates a monitoring task mt , which regulates the flow of control packets flowing through cc_{lb} and cc_{rb} . A pair of message queues are used to keep track of the messages flowing as input and output to the bridging monitor through these channels, respectively denoted in_{lb} , out_{lb} , in_{rb} and out_{rb} .¹² The monitoring task enqueues packets intended for lb and rb to out_{lb} and out_{rb} , whereas draws packets issued by lb and rb from in_{lb} and in_{rb} , respectively. A pipeline of packet handlers is used by mt for the marshalling of output packets, as well as for the unmarshalling of packets to be added to the input queues. Any control packet cp received as input is handled by mt , on the basis of the enforcement mechanism introduced in Section 5.2. Therefore, on receipt of a publishing request from lb and rb , the applicable policies are derived and checked. Such policies are stored within kvd_{lb} and kvd_{rb} , the key value datastores of the connected ecosystems.

The proposed framework reuses the same criteria adopted in [11] for the modeling of access control policies and user preferences within the datastores, as it has been shown that these favor a very efficient execution of the queries that derive all per request applicable policies and preferences. The interested reader can refer to [11] for more details.

¹⁰Local monitors are extended version of the enforcement monitor presented in [11]. Therefore, we do not report here their details, referring the interested reader to [11].

¹¹We remind that lb denotes the local broker that has been configured as a bridging broker specifying bm as connection target.

¹² in and out denote the verse of the flow from the monitor perspective, whereas lb and rb denote the broker associated with the queue.

Figure 3: Bridging monitor architecture

7. Experiments

In this section, we experimentally evaluate the efficiency of the proposed enforcement mechanism with two experiment sets. Our experiments refer to an application scenario characterized by two MQTT based interconnected ecosystems. One of the local brokers has been configured to operate as a bridge that considers the other broker as a connection target. Brokers are instances of Mosquitto v.1.4.10¹³, a popular MQTT broker. We assume that MQTT clients operating within the local ecosystems are handled by 100 users, each managing 1 to 4 clients. Clients are distributed between the two ecosystems in such a way that any user who handles a client in one ecosystem cannot handle a client in the other one. Clients distribution is carried out on the basis of three *configurations*. In the first configuration, the target ecosystem only includes publisher clients, whereas the connecting one only subscribers. In the second configuration, the distribution criterion is inverted, whereas, in the third one, publishers and subscribers are equally distributed between the two ecosystems.¹⁴ For each configuration, we consider three *deployment options*, each involving a different number of clients. The first option refers to a client set of 20 publishers and 20 subscribers, the second to 100 publishers and 100 subscribers, whereas the third one involves 200 publishers and 200 subscribers. To more easily make reference to the tested deployment settings, we refer to them as *scenarios* and we use the notation $S_{i,j}$, where $i, j \in [1, 2, 3]$, to denote the scenario corresponding to the i -th deployment option of the j -th configuration. For instance, $S_{2,3}$ refers to a scenario where 100 publishers and 100 subscribers are equally distributed between the two ecosystems. The considered scenarios are summarized in Table 2.

In the considered deployments, publisher clients have been configured to send 1 publishing request per second, whereas a single subscription request is issued by each subscriber client. Moreover, clients have been configured to issue publishing and subscription requests specifying all the same Quality of Service level (QoS).¹⁵

The routing activities of the bridging broker are regulated by the bridging monitor (cfr. Figure 2). This monitor intercepts and possibly alters the flow of the messages exchanged by the brokers on the basis of the access control policies and user preferences which have been specified within the local ecosystems. The specified access control policies, 80 per ecosystem, have been defined in such a way that, 40 policies constrain the local brokers ability to forward messages to the other ecosystem, whereas the remaining 40 constrain the local brokers ability to receive messages published in the other ecosystem. User preferences have been defined in such a way that each user specifies at most one preference which constrains the corresponding ecosystem’s broker ability to forward messages to the other ecosystem.

Our experiments aim at assessing the enforcement overhead, by measuring the *transmission time*, namely the time spent by a message published in one of the ecosystems to reach a rightful subscriber, and the packets *throughput*, considered as the number of control packets which are handled per second.

Experiment 1. Our first set of experiments consider a scenario where neither of the two ecosystems is equipped with an enforcement monitor, therefore local clients are directly connected to the respective brokers. The bridging monitor and the clients are hosted by desktop PCs equipped with i7 64-bit Quad Core CPU and 16 GB of RAM, whereas the local brokers by Raspberry Pi 3 Model B devices (equipped with a 64-bit Quad Core CPU and 1 GB of RAM).

In order to analyze the enforcement overhead, for each scenario, we compare the transmission time measured in a deployment devoid of the bridging monitor, with a deployment where the monitor is active. Two cases per scenario are considered, where all clients issue their publishing and subscription requests specifying QoS 0 and 2, respectively.

Figure 4 shows the transmission time and the overhead measured for each considered case, as well as the average analysis time required by the bridging monitor to analyze the control packets issued by local brokers. The lower part of each bar shows the transmission time related to deployments lacking the bridging monitor, whereas the upper part shows the transmission time in deployments where the monitor is active, and the corresponding time overhead. The average analysis time (per control packet) is represented by horizontal lines overlying the transmission

¹³<https://mosquitto.org/>

¹⁴We remind that the connecting ecosystem is the one hosting the bridging broker, whereas the other one is the target ecosystem.

¹⁵An MQTT client can require that specific message delivering guarantees are satisfied (see <https://docs.oasis-open.org/mqtt/mqtt/>).

Table 2: Testing scenarios

Scenario	Connecting ecosystem		Target ecosystem	
	#publishers	#subscribers	#publishers	#subscribers
S _{1,1}	0	20	20	0
S _{2,1}	0	100	100	0
S _{3,1}	0	200	200	0
S _{1,2}	20	0	0	20
S _{2,2}	100	0	0	100
S _{3,2}	200	0	0	200
S _{1,3}	10	10	10	10
S _{2,3}	50	50	50	50
S _{3,3}	100	100	100	100

time bars.

Overall the time overhead related to cases with QoS 2 is always below 45ms, whereas the one related to QoS 0 is below 37ms, showing reasonably good performances of the bridging monitor. This behavior is due to the number of control packets that are exchanged per single publishing request, which, with QoS 2, is higher than with QoS 0. As a matter of fact, when QoS 2 is specified, for each publishing request, the local brokers also exchange the control packets cp_{PRC} , cp_{PRL} , and cp_{PC} . However, the analysis of these control packets requires less time than the analysis of publishing requests (i.e., cp_{PB} , namely the only ones involved in measuring cases specifying QoS 0), as these packets, once intercepted and recognized by the monitor, are directly forwarded to the respective broker. The low processing time of these packets lowers the average analysis time of each measuring case. For this reason, for each scenario, the transmission time related to QoS 2 measuring case is higher than QoS 0 case, whereas the trend is inverted for the measured average analysis time. This scheme can be observed with any analyzed scenario. The lowest transmission times have been measured in scenarios referring to the first deployment option (e.g., S_{1,3}). The times grow in scenarios that refer to the second deployment option (e.g., S_{2,3}) and even more in scenarios referring to the third option (e.g., S_{3,3}). This behavior is due to the number of clients involved, and the volume of messages that need to be handled by the bridging broker and the bridging monitor. In contrast, the comparison of scenarios referring to the same deployment option but different configurations show negligible time variations.

For each considered case, the red bar in Figure 5 shows the throughput of the bridging monitor, whereas the blue bar the throughput of the broker in deployments devoid of the monitor. The trends in Figure 5 are similar to those observed for the transmission time analysis. Due to the analysis of policies and preferences that regulate the transit of any control packet, the rate of packets that is handled is lower than in scenarios with no enforcement mechanism. However, the observed rates combined with the previously considered transmission times (see Figure 4) appear as a reasonably good result.

Figure 4: First experiment: transmission time analysis

Figure 5: First experiment: throughput analysis

Experiment 2. In the second set of experiments each of the interconnected ecosystems also includes an enforcement monitor that regulates the ecosystem internal communication. Therefore, the considered system architecture corresponds to the one shown in Figure 3 and discussed in Section 4. The bridging monitor and the clients are hosted by desktop PCs, equipped with i7 64 bit Quad Core CPU and 16 GB of RAM, whereas the MQTT brokers of the two ecosystems are hosted by two Raspberry Pi 3 Model B devices (64 bit Quad Core and 1 GB RAM), which also host the local monitors.

In this second set of experiments, we aim at assessing the enforcement overhead introduced by the combined work of the local and bridging monitors.

The diagram in Figure 6 shows, for each considered case, the transmission time related to a deployment devoid of enforcement monitors, which is matched against the transmission time measured in a deployment where all monitors are active.

Overall the transmission time is always below 94ms, whereas the time overhead always below 89ms. Therefore, the addition of the local monitors causes a reasonably contained growth of the transmission time and the time overhead wrt the first set of experiments. The same trends that have been observed in Figure 4 are also visible in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Second experiment: transmission time analysis

Figure 7: Second experiment: throughput analysis

Finally, the diagram in Figure 7 shows the measured throughput. For each case, the red bars show the throughput of the bridging monitor, whereas the blue bars show the throughput of the broker in deployments devoid of the monitor.

The trends visible in Figure 7 are aligned with the ones observed with the first set of experiments (see Figure 5). However, in this case, due to the filtering operated by the joint work of the local monitors, a lower ratio of control packets per second reaches the bridging monitor (cfr. Figure 5).

Overall, the experiments show an enforcement overhead that is always reasonably contained, even in scenarios where data sharing across ecosystems is regulated by

three monitors.

8. Related work

The great majority of access control models which have been proposed in the literature allow regulating the communication of IoT devices operating in a single ecosystem. For instance, the CapBAC model [19] relies on users tokens, referred to as capabilities, which specify users access privileges for specific objects. A user who aims at accessing an object needs to submit his/her access request along with his/her capabilities to a Policy Decision Point. Hernandez et al. [20] present an implementation of CapBAC according to the centralized, centralized & contextual and distributed architectural styles.

Several extensions of RBAC have also been designed for IoT. For instance, the trust-based extension proposed in [21] allows handling the privileges of a user on the basis of his/her role, and the trustworthiness of the group of users to whom the same role has been assigned. Fernandez et al. [22] propose to complement the authorization process of RBAC with OAuth 2.0 based authentication. OAuth tokens are used to identify a subject who has issued an access request by means of an IoT device, along with his/her roles. A few extensions of RBAC aim at supporting context-aware policies, such as [23], which exploits model driven engineering technologies for policy specification and enforcement.

UCON based solutions for IoT have been less extensively studied than approaches based on CapBAC and RBAC (e.g., see [1]), and most of them target purpose specific application scenarios. For instance, La Marra et al. [10] proposes a UCON framework designed for smart home applications, whereas in [24], the same authors propose an approach to enforce UCON based access control within an MQTT ecosystem. On the other hand, Guoping and Wentao [25] propose an approach that allows regulating the access to sensed data on the basis of the trustworthiness of IoT devices and application services.

Finally, several ABAC approaches have been recently defined. For instance, Gabillon et al. [26, 27] propose an ABAC model to regulate clients communication within a single MQTT ecosystem. Although adopting different implementation strategies, the framework in [26, 27] is essentially aligned with the approach originally presented in [11]. Healthcare Plane [28] is an ABAC model specifically designed for the remote healthcare monitoring domain, which relies on the NIST NGAC Framework [29] for policy management.

However, none of the abovementioned proposals aims at controlling data sharing among different ecosystems, which is the focus of the current paper. We are only aware of a single attempt, by Carranza and Fong [15], to regulate data sharing among interconnected brokers. This approach is built on top of an event-based architecture [30], which enables the communication of interconnected message brokers. Brokers interaction is regulated

by scoping rules that constrain the range of the authorized receivers of any message to be routed. The approach relies on *brokering policies*, namely access control rules that constrain the brokers ability to propagate messages received through a channel to other channels. The approach has been implemented exploiting an *ad-hoc* modified version of Mosquitto.¹³ Differently from [15], our framework: i) supports context aware policies, ii) enforces user preferences, and iii) can be used with heterogeneous MQTT brokers.

In recent years, research has also extensively studied access control solutions for cloud enabled IoT applications. Alshehri and Sandhu [4] propose ACO, a reference architecture to integrate access control into cloud enabled IoT applications. In [8], ACO has been used to support the enforcement of ABAC policies, whereas, [5] shows how ACO can favor the integration of enforcement mechanisms for different access control models into AWS IoT.¹⁶ Fernandez et al. [6] propose a framework that allows users to specify privacy preferences regulating device level data collection, and access control policies that constrain data-sharing in the cloud. Gupta et al. [7] propose an ABAC model specific for smart vehicle ecosystems. The model supports access control policies regulating the access to data generated by groups of vehicles located in given zones, and user privacy preferences, which allow users to customize notification services. The authors also discuss a prototype implementation of their model for AWS IoT [7]. All these approaches rely on devices capable of managing connections with cloud services. In contrast, our framework does not rely on a cloud based infrastructure, and is suited to devices with limited computational capacity.

9. Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented an ABAC framework to control data sharing among interconnected MQTT based IoT ecosystems. The framework integrates an enforcement monitor specifically designed to be easily integrated into MQTT deployments. The experimental analysis has shown a reasonably low enforcement overhead in different scenarios.

Our work is progressing in several directions. To favor the adoption of our framework in large scale scenarios, we are investigating paralleling and load balancing techniques to automatically split up the enforcement mechanism among multiple monitors. We are also working at complementing the framework with tools for policy and user preference management. In addition, we are developing a monitoring tool to assess the effects of the specified policies and preferences.

Acknowledgment

This work has received funding from CONCORDIA, the Cybersecurity Competence Network supported by the

European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement No 830927, and from RAIS (Real-time analytics for the Internet of Sports), Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks (ITN), un-der grant agreement No 813162. The content of this paper reflects only the authors' view and the Agency and the Commission are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

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